

Affixation across Arabic and English languages

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Abstract

The affixation phenomena in Arabic and English is an effort to be explored in this study. This study incorporates all the main components of speech, including nouns, verbs, adjectives, and adverbs. It uses comparative language research to highlight both similarities and contrasts. When it comes to the affixation problem, this comparative research shows how varied languages are. In terms of affixation, namely infixes and suffixes, contrastive analysis reveals substantial variances rather than commonalities. As an added bonus, Arabic seems to be the only language that uses infixes in addition to a large number of suffixes. Learners and speakers may benefit from a better understanding of idiomatic expressions if they are cognizant of all these variants.

Keywords: english, arabic, affix, prefix, infix, suffix

Introduction

Before delving into the study and debate of affixation in Arabic and English, it is crucial to grasp the concepts of contrastive linguistics and contrastive analysis. Saeed and Fatihi (2011) conducted a comparative research on the inflectional affix systems in Arabic and English, and their findings provide the basis of this work. The study found both similarities and differences in these systems. What does this tell us about the similarities and differences across languages when it comes to word affixation, derivation, and inflection? If there is a difference, then how and what is the nature of that difference? Affixation is the primary focus of this research; subsequent inflections and derivations are beyond the scope of this work. The definition of "Affixation" should be considered first. When morphological affixes are attached to the roots of words, this process is called affixation. These could be anything from prefixes to suffixes. Their quantity is tiny in comparison to the entire number of roots, and they are almost useless; moreover, they cannot be used as words on their own. Affixation stands out as the most prevalent process for the creation of new words across all languages. Inflectional and derivational affixes are the two main categories. Inflectional forms cannot alter the word type since they occur after the stem. In contrast, derivational affixes not only alter the word class but also generate new words. In this section, we will examine each of them thoroughly, taking into account the differences between Arabic and English in this regard. For second language speakers and learners, this comparative analysis is a great tool for highlighting shared and unique features, pinpointing problem areas, and cutting down on distractions.

Research Method

Information is gathered from books, research, and search engine results in both English and the target language that pertain to the various affix types. According to Heigham and Croker (2009), this kind of data collecting is part of the qualitative research tradition. Evidence from studies shows that qualitative research focuses on the "how" and "structures" of a topic. Here, the researcher reads between the lines of the data to draw conclusions about the similarities and differences between the two languages' prefixes, infixes, and suffixes.

Affixation across languages

Affixation occurs in languages in several forms, including prefixes, infixes, and suffixes. There is a wide range of representations, occurrences, and frequencies for these morphemes. One of the most important methods to expand the vocabulary of any language is via the process of affixation.

Actually, it's one of the best strategies for expanding vocabulary in any language. Its primary use is in constructing new parts of speech. The alteration of the same word's lexical meaning is an additional function. Learning about these affixations and comparing how often they appear in different languages will help users and learners understand the structure and function of languages.

Prefixes in English and Arabic

Words that have morphemes that come before the root are called prefixes. Research shows that languages have unique morphology and affixation systems, but that there are also commonalities across them. Some languages are thought to be derivational, while others are said to be concatenative; Arabic is supposedly one of the former and English the latter. This may be considered a key distinction between the two languages. Here, in English, removing a prefix from a word might change its meaning, but in Arabic, this is not the case since Arabic words retain their original meaning even after having their prefixes removed. Consider the following English words: "disobey," "unhappy," "rewrite," "misunderstand," "irregular," "inanimate," "immature," and so on. Each of these words is an example of a different part of speech, but removing the prefix from each of them would completely flip their meaning on its head while retaining their exact grammar form. The Arabic term "Alkitab" (الكتاب), meaning "the book," differs from English words in that the prefix "Al" appears with almost every Arabic noun.

appropriate names, in particular those of locations. The meaning remains unchanged or even reversed when the definite article 'the', which is represented by al ال, is eliminated. No modification would be made to the meaning or word class. The addition of the prefix 'Ista' to other Arabic words, as 'istakbr' اِسْتَكْبَرَ meaning 'show proud,' is another example. What about 'sa'azhab'? In order to construct the present tense of a verb in the past tense, such as "Yanam" in the sentence "to sleep," the prefix "يأذهب" is often appended to the verb. In the first instance, 'KABAR' كَبَرَ (v) is the stem, whereas 'KIBR' is the noun. The meaning of words is unchanged when the prefix 'ist' اِسْت is removed. There is very little evidence that the 'Ya' prefix is used to indicate the past tense in Arabic; in fact, the prefix is more often associated with the present tense. As an example, the verb 'yaqra' يَقْرَأ read (present) is formed by attaching the prefix 'ya' to the past tense of 'qara' قَرَأ read (past), meaning reading at this very now. Here, keep in mind that removing ist, sa, and Ya from the pre-verb position just changes the tense; the part of speech or word class remain same. So, I might say that Arabic and English are clearly dissimilar in this regard since prefixes in English have a different function. Since this document does not address all of the Arabic dialects, the examples of prefixes used here are all taken from standard Arabic.

Infixes in English and Arabic

Next, we have infix affixation, which refers to morphemes that are frequently situated within the stem. Given its rarity and seeming lack of observability, I might think this kind of affixation may be intriguing to researchers. Student familiarity with this affix is lower than that with others, and research shows that this kind of morphemes is uncommon and restricted in most languages (Russelle, 1975), including English. Nevertheless, infixes may be found in a wide variety of word and morphological formative contexts, notwithstanding their rarity. It was Yu (2006). According to Yu, infixes are most often found around the word's stem or root. The use of infixes in any language necessitates the presence of prefixes and suffixes, according to Greenberg (1966), who argues that no language uses infixes solely. However, in contrast to English, Arabic does not have a strict restriction on infixes. That is to say, you'll hear them more often in Arabic than English. Take the word كَتَب 'katib' (writer) as an example; it is formed from the root word كَتَب 'k-t-b', and the infixes a-i are used to make nouns (Nida, 1949). Another example is the Arabic phrase 'بضارب' which means 'to quarrel' the 'ا' letter in the middle is considered as an infix suggesting a present tense because the root of the verb is ضَرَب 'quarreled'. In Arabic, infixes may take the shape of a letter or morpheme that grows in the word's centre. The {t} ت is a frequent infix in Arabic that is often used as a reflexive of the form {I}. Words in Arabic cannot start with a cluster, hence an epenthetic {a} prefix is inserted after the first consonant of the root. The sentence "he worked hard" might be paraphrased as "he strove" and used as an example. Arabic is unique among languages in its use of infixes to convey concepts like gender, number, and tense. Although native English speakers may sometimes coin new words with infix forms, the English language is generally believed to lack an infix system.

to express oneself strongly, as in kanga-bloody-roo (Crystal, 1997). Researchers have shown that English has very few real infixes, and those that do tend to be more obscure or reserved for specialised terminology or informal speech. We may state that

certain words in English undergo infixation, but that this process is restricted and that no constrained morphemes are infixable. For Arabic speakers, the broken plural is yet another infixation pattern. According to research, Arabic has a more common occurrence of broken or irregular plural than English does. The plural form of words like شُجُب 'shu'oub' (people) and نَفْس 'nafs' (soul) and نَفْس 'nufuus' are represented by the morpheme 'ن' 'wu,' which is infix in the root of these words. An additional way that plural nouns may be infixated with "aa" is in the following examples: بئر 'bi'er' (well), pl اَبَار 'abaar' (wells), رَجُل 'rajulun' pl رِجَال 'rijaal', etc.

Suffixes in English and Arabic

Finally, we reach the third and most prevalent kind of affixation: the suffix. A suffix is a collection of letters (one or more morphemes) appended to the end of a word that often changes its meaning or alters its grammatical function. I could stress how common suffixes are as affixes in almost every language, but notably in the two languages we're comparing and contrasting here. These suffixes are used in many ways in both Arabic and English. In this case, I may make the case that students of a language might benefit from paying attention to these suffixes because they provide hints about the meaning of words and the role they play in the language. Since this kind of affixation is crucial to understanding the origin and inflection of words, we want to go into it more. Words like "less," "ence," "ness," "ic," "ion," "al," "ly," "ism," "ist," "s," "ify," "sion," "ed," "ate," "ful," "ing," "less," "er," "ish," "able," "dom," "ant," "hood," "ship," and many more may be learned from instances like these. Once linked to roots, their primary role is to alter the word class, however this is not always the case. However, not all suffixes have the same effect; for example, "treat" (v) becomes "treatment" (n) while "maintain" (v) becomes "maintenance" (n). Suffixes such as 'hood' and 'ship,' which are known as class-keeping derivational suffixes, do not alter the word class. They serve the purpose of maintaining the same class and are appended to names. The presence of certain suffixes at the end of words indicates that they are nouns. Words like "interesting" (from "interested") and "amazing" (from "wonder") are examples of adjectives that are formed by adding certain suffixes to nouns. Words with these suffixes at the end make them easier to understand and employ for language learners since they show them what part of speech they are. It should be noted that English roots may take more than one suffix at a time; for example, the noun "person-al-ity" is formed by adding two suffixes to the end of the word (Kharma & Hajjaj, 1989). In a similar vein, verbs and nouns in Arabic often have one of two fundamental types of suffixes appended to them. Also, the Arabic language has a characteristic that lets you append up to three suffixes to a word stem at the same time. As an example, in the word فَاَسْقِيْهَاكُمُوهُ the prefix ف 'fa' is connected to the verb اَسْقَى 'irregated', the initial suffix نا 'na' acts as a subject, and the first object of the transitive verb اَسْقَى 'kmu.' is

'irregular' and 'h' constitute the second item. According to some linguists, Arabic is one of the most challenging languages in terms of grammar, morphology, and word inflections—and that's saying something considering how complicated Arabic words are. The plural morpheme is another type of suffixation. For example, in the verb يَضْرِب 'he quarrels,' the subject would be changed to يَضْرِبُونَ, and the suffix 'ون' 'uun' would be added to indicate plurality. The fact that Arabic has two forms of plurals—the sound plural and the broken plural—deserves special attention. The former occurs

more often than the latter. For example, in the phrase "جالسون هم" meaning "they (males) are sitting" and "هن جالسات" meaning "they (females) are sitting," sound plurality is created in Arabic by adding *uun* to the masculine or *aat* to the feminine. The next section delves more into the topic of plurality in both languages. Dual formation, like 'two books' *كتابين* (accusative case) or *كتابان* (nominative case), is another kind of suffixation in Arabic. Nouns with the suffix *ein* *ين* or *aan* *فن* added to them provide a dual meaning and are considered more common forms of affixation. Another distinctive feature of Arabic that sets it apart from other languages is its dual nature, which distinguishes it not just from English but also from a great number of others. Possessive pronouns, which are appended to the end of names in Arabic to indicate ownership or property, are another kind of affixation. As an example, the term 'beitahu' may be used to describe his dwelling, where the suffix 'hu' is appended to the word 'house'. As an example, *بيتهم* 'beitahum' means 'their home' and is another possessive pronoun used as a suffix. The possessive pronoun *un* 'un' indicates that the possessor is feminine rather than male, as in *بيتهن* 'beitahunn'. So, there is another possessive pronoun. As an example, "I wrote the lesson" may be expressed as "الدرس كتبت", a verb in the nominative case that often has the suffix "ت" appended to it to indicate that the speaker really performed the activity.

Plural as a Suffix in Arabic and English

Because of its widespread use in both languages, I choose to classify plurality as a distinct suffix. Despite their similarities in what may be considered regular and irregular plural forms, these languages handle affixes of this sort differently. The topic of plurality is more intricate in Arabic than in English, and discussing it in such a little space would not allow us to do it justice. Nevertheless, we will make an effort to touch on some relevant parts of the subject in both languages. A broad variety of classes in Arabic, including verbs and adjectives, as well as nouns and pronouns, may take the plural form as a suffix. Words may be either sound or broken when pluralized; the former usually entails changing the singular stem internally, such in "kanzu" (treasure) to "kunuuz" (pluralized). Adding the feminine or masculine suffix *+uun* or *+aat* to a typically unaltered stem forms the sound plural. The plural of nouns will be covered first, followed by verbs and adjectives. We have established that noun plurals can either be sound or broken. The masculine gender of the noun "player" (*العبد* *laa'betun'*, pl *العبات* 'laa'bat') is formed by adding the suffix "een" *ين*, while the feminine gender of the noun "player" (*العبة* *laa'betun'*, pl *العبات* 'laa'been') is formed by adding the suffix "aat" *ات* in the case of sound plural only (Al-Galayani, 2011). The feminine gender of a masculine word in Arabic may be derived simply by adding the letter 'eh' to it.

To make the plural of feminine, add the *'aat* suffix. This may be seen as an example of affixation, a property of the single feminine gender. Just as we discussed before, another example would be the teacher's name 'mudarris' (male), feminine 'mudarrisa' (female), and masculine plural 'mudaresuun' (female) and feminine plural 'mudarrisaat' (female). Here, the suffix *un* 'uun' indicates feminine plural while the suffix *aat* indicates masculine plural. The 'ey' suffix is another one used in Arabic nouns. *الملعب الى* 'العبي' *أنث* 'العبي' where the 'ي' is the suffix connected to the noun "العبي". This plural morpheme is added to nouns in the nominative case at the end of the word. In some nominative circumstances, the

Arabic parsing of the word's (noun's) placement in the sentence allows for the substitution of another suffix 'و' 'wa' for this one.

The plural phenomenon does not apply to Arabic adjectives, in contrast to their English counterparts. Like nouns, these adjectives may be pluralized. According to McCarthy and Prince (1999), Arabic nouns and adjectives have a gender, plurals are formed using various inflectional suffixes, and internal changes are rare. As an example, the adjective *طيب* 'tayyib' denotes male singularity, whereas the plural form *طيبون* 'tayyibuun' denotes masculine plurality, with the *uun* suffixed. Just as we have seen in nouns, feminine plurals are made by adding 'aat' *ات* to the end of adjectives. For example, 'tayyibatun' (feminine) may be pluralized as *بيات* 'tayyibaat' and similar forms can be formed in other cases.

Another key distinction between Arabic and English is the ability to pluralize verbs, which is not the case in English. Just as in Arabic, English verbs may have suffixes added to indicate tenses, but gender cannot be changed in this way. As an instance, the word *cut* may be made into 'they cut' by adding *un* 'uun' to it, while the feminine plural of verbs like this is produced by adding one letter *na* 'na', as in 'they cut' *يقطضن* 'yaqta'na'. In this context, it is important to note that the plural feminine suffix of verbs, *na* 'na', differs from that of nouns and adjectives, *aat* 'aat'. The broken plural is Arabic's second kind of plural. According to Al-Ghalayani (2011), the diminution of Arabic letters is responsible for the formation of the broken plural. In contrast to the uncommon occurrence of the English irregular plural, the broken plurals (irregular) in Arabic are widely and regularly used (Abu-Chacra, 2007). Take the broken plural of "man" (*رجل*) and "men" (*رجال*) as an example. Similarly, "soul" (*نفس*) and "souls" (*نفوس*) are also examples. As mentioned before, the plural in these two instances is created by infixing "aa" and "uu" afterwards. When it comes to irregular plurals, Arabic has a lot of regulations, unlike English, which doesn't really have any.

The concept of plurality in Arabic and English is different. There are some shared features, but there are also important differences. Unlike Arabic, pluralism may only be used in nouns and not in any other part of speech. There are two types of plural nouns in English: regular and irregular (Azaar, 1999). More people use the regular forms than the irregular ones. Adding the inflectional morphemes *-s* or *-es* to the singular noun is all that's needed in regular forms. Additional specialised derivational and inflectional research is required to clarify the factors that govern the use of these suffixes to names in accordance with the last letter of each noun. The fact that certain nouns take the morpheme *-s*, like *book* (sing) and *kooks* (pl), while others take the morpheme *-es*, like *box* (sing) and *boxes* (pl), is significant here. Here, it's very evident that The regular nouns may be modified to become plural nouns by adding the suffixes *-s* and *-es*. Additionally, it should be noted that the plural forms of *-s* or *-es* may be joined to another preceding suffix to create a second suffix, for instance, *work-er-s* or *weak-ness-es*.

In contrast to regular plurals, irregular plurals may use morphemes other than *-s* or *-es*, undergo internal stem alterations, and even lack a suffix on occasion (Leiber, 2009). Latin and Greek are common sources for inflectional suffixes like *-I*, *-ae*, and *(r)en*. The following instances utilise them: "mouse," "mice," "vertebrae," "child," etc. Another thing to keep in mind is that certain nouns, like sheep and deer, are plural in origin, while others are considered zero-suffix since they do not have a suffix or vowel (Carstairs, 2002).

Compared to Arabic, the irregular plural form is much more restricted in English.

To review, both Arabic and English utilise plurals as an affixation; both languages may operate in both regular (sound) and irregular (broken) plurality with the use of suffixes and infixes. Arabic stands apart from English due to its extensive use of irregular plurals and its ability to pluralize (affix) additional elements of speech, including adjectives and verbs, which is not the case in English.

Conclusion

Affixation as it occurs in Arabic and English is the primary focus of this article. In this article, we have looked at the several affixation forms found in Arabic and English. There are some shared characteristics between the two systems of plural affixation (regular and irregular), but there are also numerous key distinctions. Each language seems to have its own unique method of affixation production, as we have seen, rather than universal clear-cut guidelines for the utilisation of the affixation phenomena in both languages. In this article, we will look at the several affix types in Arabic and how they differ from their English equivalents. This study has addressed the qualitative data acquired and organised it in a way that serves the objective of comparing and examining linguistic variances. The results of this comparative study show that when it comes to affixation and infixation specifically, there are many notable distinctions rather than commonalities. The gender and regularity of Arabic's plural affixes also give the language a distinct flavour.

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